

Fracture Behavior and Toughness of Helical Fiber Reinforced Composite Metals

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ABSTRACT

The present study has been undertaken to examine the effects of using helical fibers instead of straight fibers as the reinforcing component on the fracture behavior and notch-sensitivity of composite metals. In this experiment helical tungsten fibers of 150 μm in dia. have been embedded in a copper matrix by electrodeposition and vacuum hot-pressing techniques. The volume fraction of the fiber was from 0.039 to 0.089. Specimens, both un-notched and single edge notched, were tensile-tested. Their fracture behavior and fracture toughness were investigated. Observations of fracture surfaces and fiber matrix interaction were made.

It has been found that an increase of fracture strain and larger fracture toughness with nearly the same strength could be obtained for the helical fiber composites as compared with the straight fiber composites.

INTRODUCTION

Straight fibers have usually been used in the fabrication of fiber reinforced composite metals, such as boron-aluminum and tungsten-copper. Although the stiffness and strength of these composites reinforced with straight fibers are very large along the direction of fibers, their failing strains are generally small (1-2 %) and they are nearly elastic up to failure. Therefore it has been suspected that their toughness might be insufficient especially under severe impact conditions.

It has been considered that some modifications of the geometrical shape of fibers, such as twisting or crimping, would increase the ductility and toughness of such composites at a small expense of stiffness. Thus, the present series of work has been undertaken to examine the effect of using helical fibers instead of straight fibers as the reinforcing component on the fracture behavior of composite metals. The copper-tungsten system has been chosen for this work, because this composite has long been a representative object of investigation in this field and its mechanical properties are relatively well understood.

Some of our preliminary results (1-9) have already been reported elsewhere. This paper reports the result of experiments on the tensile fracture behavior of composite specimens, both notched and un-notched, consisting of a copper matrix and helical tungsten fibers.

Photo. 1 Appearance of helical tungsten fiber.

θ : Helical Angle (78.4°)
 D_h : Helical Diameter
 P : Helical Pitch (2.29mm)
 D_t : Tungsten Fiber Diameter
 r_h : Helical radius (0.075mm)

Fig. 1 Geometrical parameters and constants in helical fiber.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

(1) Helical tungsten fibers

Pure tungsten fiber of $150\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter was obtained commercially. It was closely wound on to a mandrel of $0.5\ \text{mm}$ in diameter. The closely wound helix with a straight tail was pulled successively through stainless tubes of $350\ \mu\text{m}$ and $240\ \mu\text{m}$ in internal diameter, once and twice respectively, under a constant tension ($9.8\ \text{N}$).

To specify the geometrical shape of the helix, several parameters are defined as shown in Fig. 1. These parameters were measured by taking scanning electron micrographs. The measured values of the parameters for the helix used in this experiment are shown in Fig. 1. The appearance of the helical fiber is shown in Photo. 1(a) and (b).

(2) Composite fabrication

Electroplating and vacuum hot-pressing processes were employed for composite fabrication.

(i) Electroplating and fiber alignment

Helical tungsten fibers were cleaned in agitated ethyl alcohol and rinsed by water. In order to avoid deformation and damage of fibers during hot-pressing, they were uniformly electroplated with copper about $30\ \mu\text{m}$ in thickness. The standard copper electrolyte was used with a current density of $500\ \text{A/m}^2$ at $298\ \text{K}$. To maintain fiber alignment and spacing, 21 pieces of electroplated fiber were aligned parallel with equal spacings over a width of $9.5\ \text{mm}$ on a sheet of copper foil and fixed by polystyrene binder.

(ii) Hot-pressing

The sheet of copper foil fixed with the tungsten fibers was sandwiched between several sheets of the same pure copper foil (99.9%) of $70\ \mu\text{m}$ in thickness and put into a graphite mold. Prior to hot-pressing polystyrene binder was evaporated at about $573\ \text{K}$ in vacuum. Hot-pressing was carried out at $913\ \text{K}$ for 15 min with a pressure of $30\ \text{MPa}$ under a vacuum of $1.33 \times 10^{-3}\ \text{Pa}$ and the composite was cooled in the furnace. The volume fraction of fiber in the composite was controlled by its thickness, i.e., the number of sheets of copper foil.

(iii) Preparation of tensile specimens

The hot-pressed composites were cut and the surface was polished by emery paper to a prescribed thickness for the test specimen. The polished specimens were annealed at $723\ \text{K}$ under a vacuum of $1.33 \times 10^{-3}\ \text{Pa}$ for 2 h for the purpose of relieving the residual stresses in the matrix due to cutting and polishing processes.

In order to protect grips of the specimen and to minimize failure at those parts, $1\ \text{mm}$ thick aluminum plate tabs were bonded to the ends of the specimen using adhesive.

The profile of the un-notched specimen for tensile testing is shown in Fig. 2(a). For fracture toughness measurement, specimens were notched at one side by an electrical discharge machine. The average size of the radius of notch root was 100 μm . The profile of the notched specimen is shown in Fig. 2(b).

For the purpose of comparison, composite specimens reinforced with straight fibers, both notched and un-notched, were prepared by the same fabrication process

(3) Volume fraction

To measure the volume fraction of the composites, the thickness (t) and width (w) of the specimen were measured at 15 points and the average was taken over 13 points, discarding the maximum and minimum values. Volume fractions of the tungsten fiber were calculated using the average values of t and w by the following equation:

$$V_f = n_f d_f^2 / tw \sin\theta$$

where, d_f and n_f were the radius of tungsten fiber and the number of fibers on the cross sectional area perpendicular to the fiber axis, respectively. In this experiment $n_f = 21$ for all the specimens reinforced with both helical and straight fibers. Volume fractions of the composites were controlled by adjusting the specimen thickness.

(4) Tensile testing of un-notched specimens

An Instron-type tensile testing machine was used to measure the stress-strain behavior of composites. Tensile tests were performed at 293 K with a crosshead movement of 0.5 mm/min, corresponding to a strain rate of about 0.01 min^{-1} . The volume fractions of the composites were varied from 0.039 to 0.089. The fracture surface was observed by a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

Straight tungsten fibers used as the material for helical fibers as well as the helical fibers themselves were also separately tensile-tested at the same testing condition as the composites.

(5) Tensile testing of notched specimens

For the purpose of measuring the fracture toughness of the composites tensile tests were performed on notched specimens. The testing machine and the test temperature were the same as for the unnotched specimens. A crosshead movement of 0.05 mm/min was used. The volume fractions of fibers, both helical and straight, were kept constant at 0.071.

To observe interaction between fibers and the matrix near the notch root, the surface of the composites parallel to the fiber axis was buffed and observed by SEM just after a sudden drop of the load was recognized.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(1) Stress-strain characteristics of helical fiber

The stress-strain curves of the bare helical fiber as well as the straight fiber used as the material for the former are shown in Fig. 3. As for the helical fiber, the stress is defined as the tensile load divided by the cross section of the fiber and the strain is defined as the fractional change of the length of the helix.

Fig. 2 Shape and dimension of test specimen and definition of X, Y, Z coordinates (in mm). (a): un-notched tensile test specimen, (b): single edge notched type tensile test specimen (w : width, c : notch depth).

Fig. 3 Stress-strain curves of the bare straight tungsten fiber, the bare helical fiber and the copper matrix.

The linear part of the stress-strain curve for the helical fiber near the origin (region I) in Fig. 3) represents the elastic or nearly elastic elongation of the helix. After the stage of elastic deformation, the fiber begins overall plastic deformation and the helix slackens, the helical angle increasing with decreasing helical diameter. This stage (region II) is represented by the upwards concave part of the stress-strain curve. The third stage (region III) corresponds to plastic elongation of the fiber itself and its fracture.

(2) Fracture behavior of composites

Some examples of stress-strain relations for composites reinforced with straight and helical fibers are shown in Fig. 4. A sudden stress drop in the stress-strain curve is considered to correspond to a fiber fracture in the matrix.

As for the composites reinforced with straight fibers, if once the first fracture of a fiber occurs, it appears to induce fracture of the other fibers and the whole composite catastrophically proceeds to the final rupture. On the other hand, as for the composites reinforced with helical fibers, after the first fracture of a fiber in the matrix the fracture of fibers gradually progresses one by one. The stress-strain curve shows a little but continuous work-hardening, being accompanied by serration caused by fracture of fibers, until a sudden drop due to the composite rupture.

Fig. 5 shows the plots of the ultimate tensile stresses and the strains at

Fig. 4 Typical stress-strain curves for plate type specimens.

Fig. 5 Relation between volume fraction and ultimate tensile stress (σ_{UC}), or strain at σ_{UC} for helical fiber composites.

Fig. 6 Relation between volume fraction and ultimate tensile stress (σ_{UC}), or strain at σ_{UC} for straight fiber composite.

those stresses (ultimate tensile strains) vs. the volume fraction of the fiber. The results of Fig. 5 are compared with those of the composites with straight fibers in Fig. 6.

As shown in Figs. 5 and 6, linear relations between ultimate tensile stresses and volume fractions, and nearly inversely proportional relations between ultimate tensile strains and volume fractions are obtained for both types of reinforcement. If the data of the both types of composites are compared at the same volume fraction, the ultimate stresses of the helical fiber reinforced composites are slightly smaller than those of the straight fiber ones. However, fairly larger ultimate strains are obtained for the helical fiber reinforced composites than those for the other type.

The fracture surfaces of the tensile-tested specimens are shown in Photo. 2. Fiber pull-outs from the matrices are observed for both types of composites. The portions of fibers pulled out are seem much larger for the composites with helical fibers than for those with straight fibers (Photo. 2(b) and (c)). Multiple necking of the helical fibers is often observed on pulled-out fibers as shown in Photo. 3. Moreover, multiple fracture of helical fibers was observed especially in specimens of the lower volume fractions.

(3) Measurement of fracture toughness

In both types of composites reinforced with straight and helical fibers, the transverse crack started from the notch root. A typical example is shown in Photo. 4.

For all the notched specimens the maximum load was obtained just before fracture of the fiber nearest the notch root. The maximum loads were measured for specimens with varied notch depths.

Plots of gross stresses (σ_c^g) against the ratio of the notch depth (c) to the specimen width (w) are shown in Fig. 7. In this figure, σ_c^g is calculated as:

$$\sigma_c^g = F_{\max} / tw$$

where, F_{\max} is the maximum load obtained from the load-crosshead displacement curve. From the result of Fig. 7 it is apparent that the helical fiber composites are less notch sensitive than the straight fiber composites.

SEM photographs of longitudinal sections parallel to the fiber axis of composites of the both types are shown in Photo. 5. These photographs were taken just after the nearest fiber to the notch root had broken. In the helical fiber

Photo. 2 SEM photographs of fracture surface. (a): straight fiber composite ($V_F=0.065$), (b)(c): helical fiber composite ((b): $V_F=0.078$, (c): $V_F=0.037$).

Photo. 3 SEM photographs shows multiple necking of helical fibers. ($V_F=0.037$).

composite (Photo. 5(b)) multiple necking of unbroken fibers a little away from the fractured fiber and splitting of the interface between a fiber and the matrix (Photo. 5(c)) are recognized. In contrast in a straight fiber composite (Photo. 5(a)), neither multiple necking nor splitting of the interface are recognized. It was reported that the multiple necking of fiber occurred after the matrix had yielded (10). Therefore, the extent of the plastic deformation zone in the matrix near the notch root of the helical fiber composite seems larger than that of the straight fiber composite. This phenomenon is presumably related to the deformation and interaction with the matrix peculiar to the helical fiber.

As a result, the helical fiber composite seems to require larger work of fracture than the straight fiber composite. That is to say, tougher composite materials could be obtained by using helical fibers instead of straight fibers.

CONCLUSIONS

The fracture behavior and fracture toughness of copper matrix reinforced with helical tungsten fibers were investigated. The results were compared with those on the straight fiber composites. The following conclusions were obtained.

Photo. 4 SEM photograph showing typical crack growth from the notch root (helical fiber composite, $c/w=0.52$).

Photo. 5 Crack path in composites ((a): straight fiber reinforced composite, (b)(c): helical fiber reinforced composite).

(1) The tensile fracture behavior of the helical fiber composite was not so catastrophic as that of straight fiber composite.

(2) Fairly larger ultimate tensile strains were obtained at small expense of ultimate tensile stresses by using helical fibers instead of straight ones.

(3) The helical fiber composite showed less notch-sensitivity in the tensile fracture test than the straight fiber composite. In the former type of composite, much larger plastic deformation zone seemed to spread from the root of the notch.

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Fig. 7 Plots of σ_c^g vs. c/w .